

Study on Marketing of Herbicide (IRIS) in Shivpuri District of Madhya Pradesh State

Mayank Sharma

P.G. Student MBA (Agribusiness Management)
Department of Agricultural Economics,
Sam Higgin bottom University of Agriculture,
Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

Jayant Zechariah

Assistant Professor,
Department of Agricultural Economics,
Sam Higgin bottom University of Agriculture,
Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract:- The Present study was conducted in the year 2022-2023 with a sample of 100 Soybean farmers in Block of Pohri district of Shivpuri. The study reveals that the market share of UPL Ltd in Shivpuri district was found to be the maximum total of 1,03,000 viz. Herbicide, followed by Insecticides, and Fungicides. The market share and key existing competitors of IRIS herbicide was found to be Patela, Sugam, Shaked, Fusiflex, Odyssey. While studying the customers it was found that customers buy agrochemicals maximum on the basis of relation with the dealers contributing followed by the quality of product, brand image, and price of the product and other source. The major constraints of marketing of IRIS herbicide were High cost of herbicide, lack of availability of information at farm level, quality of herbicide, lack of awareness and lack of field work and others.

Keywords:- Market Share, Key-existing Competitors, Brand Awareness, Customer Perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays an important role in growth of developing countries like India where agriculture contributes around 19.9% Gross Domestic Products in the year 2017. Agriculture is the backbone of Indian Economy. Ensuring food security for more than 1.23 billion Indian population with diminishing cultivable land resource is a herculean task. Soybean (*Glycine max*) is one of the most important oil crops of the world which also has tremendous importance as a food legume. Soybean occupies a premier position among agricultural crops, being the most important source of good quality concentrated proteins as well as vegetable oil. Soy oil finds a variety of uses for domestic and industrial purposes besides its use in several food preparation and animal feed. Soybean is the numero uno oilseed crop in India. Soybean has become an important oilseed crop in India in a very short period with approximately 10-million ha area under its cultivation. Major soybean growing states are Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Karnataka and Telangana. These states together contribute to about 98% of the total soybean production in the country. Madhya Pradesh since the beginning has been the major contribution to the soybean area and production, currently contributing 59% of area and production followed by Maharashtra with a contribution of 28% and 26% in terms of total area and production of the country. Meanwhile, weeds are considered one of the problems in all major soybean producing countries. Farmers maintain high soybean yield through effective control of

weeds which compete with crops for light, water and nutrients. Even with advanced technologies, producers note high losses due to interference by weeds. According to estimates, weeds, alone, cause an average reduction of 37% on soybean yield, while other fungal disease and agricultural pests accounts for 22% of losses, the use of insecticides takes the lion's share, around 65%, whereas, the use of herbicide is well around 16%. Herbicides demand in India is rising sharply could double in next three years, as an acute labour shortage makes them a cheaper option & rally in farm good prices prompts farmers to grow crop with extra care. Herbicide, in the broad action spectrum, are and will be essential tools in weed management, even for those with a great number of resistant weeds.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A. Selection of the District:

There are 50 District and 10 division in Madhya Pradesh state. Out of this Shivpuri district of Madhya Pradesh was selected for the present study based on highest production districts form Soybean.

B. Selection of Block:

There are 8 blocks in the district. Out of these Pohri was selected purposively for the study.

C. Selection of Village:

A complete list of all villages of Pohri block was obtained from the block development office. Thus, out of total villages 5% of villages were selected randomly for the present study.

D. Selection of Respondents:

From the selected village list of all the Soybean farmers obtained from the village development office in each selected village. 100 farmers were considered as respondents for the present study. The selections were done by using simple random sampling method for the purpose of the study.

E. Analytical Tools

➤ Garrett Ranking:

Garrett's Ranking Technique is applied to study the preference, change of orders of constraints and advantages into numerical scores.

(Garrett and Woodsworth, 1969):

Percentage position= [100 (Rij-0.5)]/Nj

% increase= [(New number-Original number)/Original number] x 100

Where,

Rij=rank given for ith problem by jth individual
 Nj=number of problems ranked by the jth individual

➤ *Market Share Formula:*

$$\text{Market Share (\%)} = \frac{\text{Company Sales}}{\text{Total Market Sales}}$$

➤ *Percentage Formula:*

The percentage formula is used to find the share of a whole in terms of 100. Using this formula, you can represent a number as a fraction of 100.

Percentage= (Value/Total Value) × 100

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result is a presentation of the findings of the given study, purely based on the objective:

➤ *To identify the key existing competitors and their market share in the study area.*

Table 1: Market share of Pesticides by UPL Ltd in Shivpuri District

S. No.	Pesticides	Quantity Sales (Lit.)	Market Share (%)
01.	Herbicides	65,000	63
02.	Fungicides	18,000	18
03.	Insecticides	20,000	19
	Total	1,03,000	100

Table 1 reveals that the market share of Pesticides by UPL Ltd in Shivpuri District comprises of a total quantity sale of 1,03,000 litre in which the Herbicide section

comprises of 63% of total quantity sales followed by Insecticides with 19% and Fungicides with 18% of total quantity sales in Shivpuri District.

Table 2: Key existing competitors and their market share of Herbicide by major companies in Pohri block.

Sr. No.	Company Name	Herbicide Product	Quantity Sales (Litre)	Market Share (%)	Rank
01.	UPL	IRIS	12,000	40	1
02.	SWAL	Patela	7,500	25	2
03.	Syngenta	Fusiflex	2,100	7	5
04.	Adama	Shaked	3,300	11	4
05.	BASF	Odyssey	1,500	5	6
06.	Excel	Sugam	3,500	12	3
	Total		29,900	100	

The UPL Ltd company is in competition with both national and multinational companies like Bayer, Syngenta, Du-Pont, Dhanuka, BASF, Tata chemicals, Pesticide India, etc are some of the major competitors. These companies with early entry in business of Herbicide have large customers base and were able to capture more market share. **Table 2** reveals that the highest market share i.e., 40% was found in IRIS of UPL Ltd. Company ranking on the number 1 position in Pohri block. The SWAL was the biggest competitor with the product Patela contributing with 25% of market share and with 2nd rank followed by Excel company with product Sugam having market share of 12% ranking 3rd. The other competitor like Adama (Shaked) with 11% of market share and ranking 4th, Syngenta (Fusiflex) with 7% ranking 5th, and BASF (Odyssey) with 5% ranking 6th.

IV. CONCLUSION

Agriculture occupies a dominant position in India's economy structure. India is predominantly agriculture-based country. It contributes about 19.96 percent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of our country and about 60 percent of total population engages in agriculture sector. Meanwhile weeds are considered one of the problems in all major Soyabean producing countries. Farmers maintain high Soyabean yield through effective control of weeds which compete with crops for light, water and nutrients. Even with advanced technologies, producers note high losses due to interference by weeds.

The market share of Pesticides in Shivpuri district of UPL Ltd. Company is about 1,03,000 litre comprises of herbicide with 63% market share, followed by Insecticide with 19% market share and Fungicides with 18% market share. There are many competitors for the herbicide (IRIS) in Pohri block of Shivpuri district and the UPL (IRIS) is the

major player with the sales of 40% of market share and ranking on number 1 position followed by SWAL (Patela) with 25% of market share with 2nd ranking. Excel (Sugam) contribute 12% market share rank on 3rd. the other competitors like Adama (Shaked) with 11% of market share and ranking 4th, Syngenta fusiflex with 7% and BASF (Odyssey) with 5%.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Ajayi, Oluyede OC. Pesticide use practices, productivity and farmers' health. Uni, 2000.
- [2.] Beckie, Hugh J., Michael B. Ashworth, and Ken C. Flower. "Herbicide resistance management: Recent developments and trends." *Plants* 8.6 (2019): 161.
- [3.] Chahal. H.S. and Hundal, B.S. (2011). Factors responsible for brand liking, brand loyalty and brand switching among farmers of Punjab: a study of Pesticide, *Indian Journal of Agricultural Marketing* 24(1):119-131.
- [4.] Gianessi, Leonard P. "The increase importance of herbicide in worldwide crop production." *Pest management science* 69.10 (2013): 1099-1105.
- [5.] Pike, David R., MARSHAL D. McGLAMERY, and Ellery L. Knake. "A case study of herbicide use." *Weed Technology* 5.3 (1991): 669-674.
- [6.] Poramacom, Nongnooch. "Pesticide markets and related situations in Thailand." *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences* 22.2 (2001): 205-211.
- [7.] Rüegg, W. T., Marco Quadranti, and Andreas Zoschke. "Herbicide research and development: challenges and opportunities." *Weed Research* 47.4 (2007): 271-275.
- [8.] Tandelal.(2015)To study the farmers buying behaviour on pesticides product strategies adopted by Syngenta India ltd. And its impact on consumer buying behaviour in Nanded city. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*. 1(6):1-25.